

The Wright function – numerical approximation and hypergeometric representation

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Abstract. The Wright function, which arises in the theory of the space-time fractional diffusion equation, is a very general mathematical object with diverse connections to other special and elementary functions. The paper presents a numerical integration technique for approximation of the Wright function $W(a, b|x)$ using the method of stationary phase. As a second contribution, the paper exhibits a symbolic algorithm for hypergeometric (HG) representation of the Wright function. For rational values of its first argument the function is reduced to a finite sum of HG functions and polynomials. The HG functions are themselves represented by known elementary or other special functions, wherever possible. Reference implementations of the algorithms are programmed in the open-source computer algebra system Maxima.

Keywords: Wright function · hypergeometric function · Bessel function

1 Introduction

Fractional calculus models of physical phenomena have rekindled the interest in special functions. The Wright function arises in the theory of the space-time fractional diffusion equation. It is a very general mathematical entity with diverse connections to other special and elementary functions. Notably, it provides a unified treatment of several classes of special functions, such as the Gaussian, Airy, Bessel, error functions, etc. The function was originally defined by the infinite series [9]:

$$W(a, b|z) := \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{k! \Gamma(ak + b)}, \quad z, b \in \mathbb{C}, \quad a > -1, \quad (1)$$

where $\Gamma(\sim)$ denotes the Euler's gamma function. In view of its broad applications, methods of its computation can be of general interest. The paper presents a numerical integration technique for approximation of the Wright function using the method of stationary phase for real values of the arguments and parameters. On the second place, the paper exhibits a symbolic algorithm for hypergeometric (HG) representation of the Wright function $W(a, b|x)$. For rational values of its first argument the function is reduced to a finite sum of HG functions and

polynomials. The HG functions are themselves represented by known elementary or other special functions, wherever possible. Reference implementations of the algorithms are programmed in the open-source computer algebra system Maxima.

2 Numerical approximation

Until recently, efficient numerical algorithms for Wright function's approximation were not available. The seminal works of Luchko et al. [3, 4] investigated only the case $|b| \leq 1$. Recently, also the Laplace transform inversion method was used for its approximation [1]. The present work uses a different contour determined by the requirement of stationary phase, which improves the overall numerical stability of the algorithm.

Theorem 1. *The Wright function $W(a, b|z)$ for real arguments can be computed according to the table:*

$b \backslash a$	$a < 0$	$a = 0$	$a > 0$
$b \leq 1$	$W(a, b z) = I_r(0)$	$W(a, b z) = \frac{e^z}{\Gamma(b)}$	$W(a, b z) = I_u(\epsilon^a) + P(\epsilon)$
$b = 1$	$W(a, b z) = I_r(0) + 1$		
$b > 1$	$W(a, b z) = I_r(\epsilon) + P(\epsilon)$		

where $\epsilon = \max\left(\left|{}^{a+1}\sqrt{|az|\right|}, 1\right)$ and

$$I_r(\epsilon) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{\epsilon}^{\infty} \frac{\sin\left(\frac{\sin(\pi a)z}{r^a} + \pi b\right)}{r^b} e^{\frac{\cos(\pi a)z}{r^a} - r} dr,$$

$$I_u(\epsilon) = \frac{1}{\pi a} \int_{\epsilon}^{\infty} u^{\frac{1-b}{a}-1} \sin(\sin(\pi a)z/u + \pi b) e^{\cos(\pi a)z/u - u^{1/a}} du,$$

$$P(\epsilon) = \frac{\epsilon^{1-b}}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} e^{\epsilon \cos \varphi + \cos(a\varphi)z/\epsilon^a} \cos(-z \sin(a\varphi)/\epsilon^a + \epsilon \sin \varphi + (1-b)\varphi) d\varphi.$$

Proof. The canonical complex line integral representation of the Wright function is given by the integral

$$W(a, b|z) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{H_{a-}} \frac{e^{\xi+z\xi^{-a}}}{\xi^b} d\xi = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{H_{a-}} \ker(\xi) d\xi, \quad z \in \mathbb{C}, \quad (2)$$

along a Hankel contour, which surrounds the negative real semi-axis. The starting point of the proof is a deformation of the Hankel contour into a part enclosing the pole at the origin and parts extending towards negative infinity. The Hankel integral contour can be split in three parts - the rays BA , ED and the arch BCD . Accordingly, the value of the integral can be evaluated as:

$$W(a, b|z) = \underbrace{I_{AB} + I_{DE}}_{I_r} + \underbrace{I_{BCD}}_{P_\epsilon} = \int_{AB} \ker(\xi) d\xi + \int_{BCD} \ker(\xi) d\xi + \int_{DE} \ker(\xi) d\xi.$$

The branch cut will be taken along the negative real axis. Then for the two rays AB and ED we obtain

$$ker_{AB} - ker_{ED} = \frac{2ie^{\cos(\delta)r + \frac{\cos(a\delta)z}{r^a}} \sin\left(\frac{\sin(a\delta)z}{r^a} - \sin(\delta)r + b\delta\right)}{r^b}.$$

Taking the limit $\delta \rightarrow \pi$ results in the radial contribution

$$I(\epsilon) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{\epsilon}^{\infty} \frac{e^{\frac{\cos(\pi a)z}{r^a} - r} \sin\left(\frac{\sin(\pi a)z}{r^a} + \pi b\right)}{r^b} dr. \quad (3)$$

For the arch part we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} ker_{BCD} &= \frac{ie^{\epsilon \cos(\varphi) + \frac{\cos(a\varphi)z}{\epsilon^a}} \cos\left(\frac{-\sin(a\varphi)z}{\epsilon^a} + \epsilon \sin(\varphi) - b\varphi + \varphi\right)}{\epsilon^b} \\ &\quad - \frac{\epsilon e^{\epsilon \cos(\varphi) + \frac{\cos(a\varphi)z}{\epsilon^a}} \sin\left(\frac{-\sin(a\varphi)z}{\epsilon^a} + \epsilon \sin(\varphi) - b\varphi + \varphi\right)}{\epsilon^b}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, taking the limit $\delta \rightarrow \pi$ as before we obtain the circular integral

$$P(\epsilon) = \frac{\epsilon^{1-b}}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} e^{\epsilon \cos \varphi + \cos(a\varphi)z/\epsilon^a} \cos(-(\sin(a\varphi)z/\epsilon^a + \epsilon \sin \varphi + (1-b)\varphi) d\varphi.$$

What is left is to determine the optimal value of ϵ . Here the present approach departs from the treatment of [3]. The Hölder exponent β at the origin is determined by the limit of the Hölder function $h(\xi) := \xi \frac{d}{d\xi} \log ker(\xi)$ so that $\beta = \lim_{\xi \rightarrow 0} h(\xi)$. For the Wright kernel $h(\xi) = -az/\xi^a + \xi - b$. Therefore, for $a < 0$

and $\beta = h(\xi) \Big|_{\xi=0} = -b$ and corresponds with the fact that $W(a, b|0) = 1/\Gamma(b)$.

In particular, if $b < 1$ the singularity at the origin is integrable and $\epsilon = 0$. Furthermore, for integer a and b the contour can be closed and the Cauchy theorem can be applied. Therefore, $W(-n, m|z)$ becomes a polynomial in z for integer n and m . In contrast, if $a > 0$ an essential singularity appears at the origin as the Hölder exponent diverges. For that latter case we look for the curve where the phase of the kernel is stationary to first order to minimize oscillations. This is given by the computation

$$\frac{d}{d\xi} (z/\xi^a + \xi) \Big|_{\xi=\xi_0} = \left(-\frac{az}{\xi^{a+1}} + 1\right) \Big|_{\xi=\xi_0} = 0 \implies \xi_0 = {}^{a+1}\sqrt{az}.$$

Therefore, we can take $\epsilon = |\xi_0| = {}^{a+1}\sqrt{|az|}$.

The next proposition is stated without proof in view of the space limitations.

Proposition 1. *For non negative integers n, m*

$$\Gamma(mn + b) = \Gamma(mb) m^{mn} \prod_{j=0}^{m-1} \binom{j}{m} + b \Big|_n.$$

3 Hypergeometric representation

Wherever the first parameter is rational, the Wright function can be represented by a finite sum of hypergeometric functions. The Generalized Hypergeometric (GHG) function ${}_pF_q$ will be used under the notation

$${}_pF_q \left(a_0 \dots a_{p-1}; b_0 \dots b_{q-1} \middle| z \right) := \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^r}{r!} \frac{\prod_{j=0}^{p-1} (a_j)_r}{\prod_{j=0}^{q-1} (b_j)_r}, \quad (4)$$

where $(a)_r$ and $(b)_r$ will denote rising factorials and $(a)_0 = 1$, which assumes the normalization ${}_pF_q \left(\sim; \sim \middle| 0 \right) = 1$. By convention, equal parameters in the numerator and denominator will cancel out. For positive, rational a one could obtain the representation [2]:

Theorem 2 (First HG Representation). *Suppose that $a = n/m > 0$, where n and m are co-prime. Then*

$$W \left(\frac{n}{m}, b \middle| z \right) = \sum_{r=0}^{m-1} \frac{z^r}{r! \Gamma(b + ar)} \cdot {}_1F_{m+n} \left(1; b_0 \dots b_{n-1}, c_0 \dots c_{m-1} \middle| \frac{z^m}{n^n m^m} \right), \quad (5)$$

where $b_j = r/m + (b + j)/n$, $c_j = (r + 1 + j)/m$.

The proof follows [5] and is given as a starting point for the proof of the Second Representation Theorem.

Proof. Observe that

$$W(n/m, b|z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{k! \Gamma(ak + b)} = \sum_{q=0}^{m-1} \sum_{p \geq q/m}^{\infty} \frac{z^{mp-q}}{\Gamma(mp - q + 1) \Gamma(a(mp - q) + b)},$$

since the integer k can be partitioned as $k = mp - q$, where $q = 0, \dots, m - 1$. After some algebra we obtain

$$W(n/m, b|z) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(b)} + \sum_{r=1}^m z^r \sum_{p=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^{mp}}{\Gamma(ap + ra + b) \Gamma(mp + r + 1)}.$$

Observe that for $p = 0$ the inner series coefficient is $C_r = 1/\Gamma(ra + b)\Gamma(r + 1)$, which serves as a normalization factor. Therefore, the series transforms as

$$W(n/m, b|z) = \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{z^r}{C_r} \cdot \sum_{p=0}^{\infty} \frac{C_r}{\Gamma(n(p + r/m + b/n))} \frac{z^{mp}}{\Gamma(m(p + (r + 1)/m))}. \quad (6)$$

Further, use Prop. 1 to obtain

$$\Gamma(b + aj) = \Gamma(a(j + b/a)) = \Gamma(b) \left(\frac{b}{a} \right)_j \left(\frac{b+1}{a} \right)_j \dots \left(\frac{b+a-1}{a} \right)_j a^{aj}.$$

From eq. 6 we read off $b_0 = \frac{r}{m} + \frac{b}{n}, c_0 = \frac{r+1}{m}$ with increments $1/n$ and $1/m$, respectively. Therefore, finally,

$$W(a, b|z) = \sum_{r=0}^{m-1} \frac{z^r}{r! \Gamma(b+ar)} \cdot {}_1F_{m+n} \left(1; b_0 \dots b_{n-1}, c_0 \dots c_{m-1} \middle| \frac{z^m}{n^n m^m} \right).$$

Observe that for $r = m - 1$ $c_1 = 1$. Therefore, the GHG functions reduce to ${}_0F_{m+n-1}$.

Similar formula for a negative rational a can be also given as follows:

Theorem 3 (Second HG Representation). *For $b \leq 1$ and $n \leq m$ non-negative co-prime integers*

$$W\left(-\frac{n}{m}, b|z\right) = \sum_{r=0}^{m-1} \frac{z^r}{r! \Gamma(b+ar)} {}_{n+1}F_m \left(1, b'_0 \dots b'_{n-1}; c_0 \dots c_{m-1} \middle| \frac{(-)^n z^m}{n^n m^m} \right), \tag{7}$$

where $b'_j = 1 + r/m - (b+j)/n, c_j = (r+1+j)/m, a = -n/m$.

Proof. Suppose first that $b < 1$. Let

$$W(-n/m, b|z) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(b)} + \sum_{r=1}^m \frac{z^r}{C_r} \sum_{p=0}^{\infty} \frac{C_r}{\Gamma(-np - rn/m + b)} \frac{z^{mp}}{\Gamma(mp + r + 1)},$$

where C_r was defined as above. We use the Gamma reflection formula to obtain

$$\frac{1}{\Gamma(-np - rn/m + b)} = \frac{(-1)^{np} \Gamma\left(\frac{nr}{m} + np - b + 1\right)}{\Gamma\left(b - \frac{nr}{m}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{nr}{m} - b + 1\right)}. \tag{8}$$

Therefore,

$$W(-n/m, b|z) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(b)} + \sum_{r=1}^m \frac{z^r}{C_r} \sum_{p=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{np} C_r \Gamma\left(\frac{nr}{m} + np - b + 1\right) z^{mp}}{\Gamma\left(b - \frac{nr}{m}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{nr}{m} - b + 1\right) \Gamma(m(p + (r+1)/m))}.$$

Finally, we read off the parameters $b'_j = 1 - (-r/m + (b+j)/n) = 1 + r/m - (b+j)/n$. Observe that for $r = m - 1$ $c_1 = 1$. Therefore, as before the GHG functions reduce to ${}_nF_{m-1}$.

For $b \geq 1$ a polynomial term P is also added as follows.

Definition 1 (Wright polynomials). *Define the polynomial $P_b(-a, z)$ by the integral recursion*

$$P_b(-a, z) = \int_0^z P_{b-a}(-a, x) dx + c_{b-1}, \tag{9}$$

where $c_{b-1} = 1/(b-1)!$ if b is an integer and 0 otherwise. Furthermore, define $P_0(z, -a) := 1$ and for $b < 0$ assign $P_b(z, -a) := 0$ identically.

Fig. 1. Absolute error plots for $a = 1$: A - $|J_0(x) - W(1, 1 | -x^2/4)|$, B - $|\sin(2x)/(\pi x) - W(1, 3/2 | -x^2)|$.

Theorem 4 (Third HG representation). *Suppose that a and b are rational parameters and $b \geq 1$ and $|a| \leq 1$. Then*

$$W(-n/m, b|z) = \sum_{r=0}^{m-1} \frac{z^r}{r! \Gamma(b - nr/m)} \cdot {}_{n+1}F_m \left(1, b'_0 \dots b'_{n-1}; c_0 \dots c_{m-1} \middle| \frac{(-)^n z^m}{n^n m^m} \right) + P_b(n/m, z) \quad (10)$$

where m and n are co-prime numbers.

Proof. First we prove that the arc integral results in a polynomial in z . Suppose that $b \geq 1$ is rational and $-a = n/m$ as before. Consider the arc BCD. We change variables as $\xi = \epsilon \eta^m$. We develop the integral kernel in infinite series:

$$ker = m \frac{d\eta}{\eta^{(b-1)m+1}} \epsilon^{1-b} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i=0}^j \frac{\epsilon^{\frac{im+(j-i)n}{m}} \eta^{im+(j-i)n} z^{j-i}}{i! (j-i)!}.$$

The scale-invariant part of the series is given by the members k_j for which $\epsilon^{\frac{im+(j-i)n}{m} - b + 1} = 1$. This is given by the constraint $i = \frac{(b-1)m - jn}{m-n}$. Therefore, the monomial terms are computed by the formula

$$c_j = \frac{z^{\frac{(j-b+1)m}{m-n}}}{\left(\frac{(b-1)m - jn}{m-n} \right)! \left(\frac{(j-b+1)m}{m-n} \right)!} = \frac{z^{\frac{j-b+1}{1-a}}}{\left(\frac{j-b+1}{1-a} \right)! \left(\frac{-aj+b-1}{1-a} \right)!}, \quad (11)$$

where the valid indices are given by the set $j : \left(\frac{(j-b+1)m}{m-n} \in \mathbb{N} \right) \cup \left(\frac{(b-1)m - jn}{m-n} \in \mathbb{N} \right)$. Equivalently, using the a-notation it can be seen that $a < 1$ must hold for c_j not

to vanish. On the other hand, $b - 1 \leq j \leq (b - 1)/a \cup j \in \mathbb{N}$, which is a finite set. Therefore, for a rational b the integral in eq. 2 becomes a polynomial in z .

To derive the polynomial recursion we proceed as follows. Observe that

$$W(-a, b|z) = \int_0^z W(-a, b - a|z) + 1/\Gamma(b), \tag{12}$$

so that the equation defines a recursion relationship.

Observe that for $j = b - 1$ the constant term becomes $c_{b-1} = 1/(b - 1)!$. Therefore, for non-integer b there are no constant monomials. Furthermore, consider the monomial c_j as a function of b . Differentiating eq. 11 one obtains the recursion

$$\frac{d}{dz} c_j(b) = \frac{z^{\frac{j-b+1}{1-a}-1}}{\left(\frac{j-b+1}{1-a} - 1\right)! \left(\frac{-aj+b-1}{1-a}\right)!} = \frac{z^{\frac{j-(b-a)}{1-a}}}{\left(\frac{j-(b-a)}{1-a}\right)! \left(\frac{aj-b+1}{a-1}\right)!} = c_{j-1}(b-a),$$

which is also consistent with the integral eq. 12. Therefore, the polynomial $P_b(-a, z)$ should obey the above recursion. The second argument of the Wright function mutates and therefore it is convenient that it indexes the polynomial.

For integer values of a , the hypergeometric sum disappears from eq. 10.

It should be noted that the Second and Third HG Representation theorems could not be traced to available literature. Based on these new results, we can classify the Wright functions as - 1st type (when $a > 0$); 2nd type (when $a \in [-1, 0]$, $b < 1$); and 3rd type when $b \geq 1$ and $a \in [-1, 0]$ or when a is a negative integer and b is a positive integer.

zero	w_1	w_2	w_3	w_4	w_5	w_6
error	5.9342 E-17	8.7931 E-17	2.2841 E-16	2.4453 E-17	3.204 E-17	1.2964 E-16

Table 1. Absolute errors at the first zeroes of $J_0(x)$

The utility of the above method depends on the availability of routines to calculate "ordinary" special functions, such as the Bessel, error, Gaussian etc. An illustrative example of Th. 3 can be presented for $a = -1/3$ and $b = 1/3$:

$$W(-1/3, 1/3| -z) = -\frac{z}{3} \left(I_{2/3} \left(\frac{2z^{\frac{3}{2}}}{3^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) - I_{-2/3} \left(\frac{2z^{\frac{3}{2}}}{3^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) \right) = \frac{z}{\sqrt{3}\pi} K_{2/3} \left(\frac{2z^{\frac{3}{2}}}{3^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) = -\sqrt[3]{3} \text{Ai}' \left(\frac{z}{\sqrt[3]{3}} \right). \tag{13}$$

4 Numerical Experiments

A reference implementation in the computer algebra system Maxima was developed and deposited in the Zenodo repository [8]. The library implements

two quadrature algorithms – the function *gmwright* which is implemented using the double exponential (DE) quadrature in Lisp [6], and the function *gmwright2*, which is implemented using the default Maxima QUADPACK library translated to Lisp [7]. Both QUADPACK and DE libraries can compute with user-specified precision. In addition, the library contains the function *wrightsimp*, which implements Th. 2, 3, and 3 and is written in the Maxima language. The library is available for download and testing at <https://zenodo.org/record/7871652>. Numerical experiments were performed on a 64-bit Microsoft Windows 10 Enterprise machine with configuration – Intel[®] Core[™] i5-8350U CPU @ 1.70GHz, 1.90 GHz and 16GB RAM. The algorithm shows good numerical stability for the computation of Bessel functions for intermediate values of the argument (Fig. 1). The plots in Fig. 1 have been produced using the QUADPACK *quad_qagi* (implementing seminifinite domain integration) and *quad_qag* (implementing Gauss-Kronrod quadrature formulae) routines in Maxima 5.46.0 running Steel Bank Common Lisp (SBCL) v. 2.2.2. The figure demonstrates that numerical quadrature with QUADPACK reaches machine precision. The absolute errors at the first zeroes of $J_0(x)$ are shown in Table 1.

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